

O'ZARO BOG'LANGAN POLIMERLAR ASOSIDA YANGI GIDROGELLAR SINTEZI, VA NATIJALARINI O'RGANISH

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqola bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalari ishlab chiqarish chiqindilari va mahalliy xomashyodan foydalangan holda, yuqori bo'kadigan gidrogellar olish texnologiyasi masalasiga ilmiy asoslangan bo'lib, bu mahsulot sifatini yaxshilash, ishlab chiqarish hajmini oshirish va tannarxini pasaytirish imkonini beradi.

Polimer gellari erituvchida bo'kkan uch o'lchamli o'zaro bog'langan polimerlar deb ataladi. Ular tabiiy yoki sintetik (poliakrilamid gellari, poliakril kislota va boshqalar) bo'lishi mumkin. Gel tarkibidagi erituvchi miqdori ancha yuqori bo'lishi mumkin (99,9% gacha). Gellar asosan suyuq bo'lsa-da, ular qattiq moddalar kabi o'z shakllarini ushlab turishga qodir. Buning sababi shundaki, gelni tashkil etuvchi polimer zanjirlari bitta fazoviy ramka - polimer tarmog'iga o'zaro bog'langan.

Tadqiqot materiallari va metodologiyasi

Gidrogelning ta'siri uning o'simlik atrofida namni ushlashi, bug'lanishga qarshilik ko'rsatishi va yer osti suvlarini tortishiga asoslangan. O'simlik nafaqat sug'orish va atmosfera namligidan, balki bo'kkan gidrogel suvidan ham foydalanishi mumkin. Shuningdek ishlov beriladigan o'simliklarda suv sarfini kamaytiradi. Bundan tashqari toshloq yerlarda suvning singishi katta tezlikda bo'lib, u yerda ishlatilgan gidrogel suvni ildiz atrofida tutib qola oladi.

Gidrogellarni ekin ekish vaqtida urug' bilan aralashtirib ekish kerak. Ekiladigan urug'lar bilan deyarli teng miqdorda sarflanadigan bu gidrogellar, yog'in-sochin, sug'orish vaqtida tuproqqa shimilgan suvni yutib, uni uzoq vaqt ildiz atrofida tutib, o'simlikni suv bilan ta'minlab tura oladi. Natijada yerni sug'orishlar oralig'idagi vaqt kattalashib ancha suv tejab qolinadi. Eng muhimi ekologik jihatdan zararsiz. Shuningdek gidrogellar suvni o'simlikka keyingi sug'orish vaqtigacha berib turadi. Keyingi sug'orishda gidrogel yana suvga bo'kib, o'simlikni suv bilan ta'minlashda davom etadi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Keyingi vaqtlarda gellar asosida polielektrolitlar sintezlab olinmoqda. Ba'zi polielektrolitlar qimmatbaho super absorbentlar bo'lib juda ko'p sohada qo'llaniladi. Bunday polielektrolitlarda tanlab ta'sir etish xususiyati kuchli bo'ladi. Shu sababli ham ionitlar sifatida keng qo'llanilmoqda.

Gidrogellar bilan rezina va boshqa materiallar kompozitsiyalarining yaratilishi esa gellarning qo'llanilish soxasini yanada kengaytirdi.

Foydalaniladigan quduq tubiga suv oqimini cheklash neft konlarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish va neft qazib olishni ko'paytirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar tizimidagi eng muhim muammolardan biridir. Bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta mahsuldor qatlamlari

ishlatadigan quduqlarda sug'orish notekis sodir bo'ladi - suv ko'proq o'tkazuvchan qatlamlar va oraliq qatlamlardan o'tadi. Ko'pgina hollarda, bunday qatlamlar orqali suv oqimi shunchalik kuchliki, quduq butunlay suv bosganga o'xshaydi. Bunday sharoitda alohida qatlamlarning notekis rivojlanishi sodir bo'ladi. Konlar va quduqlarning normal ishlashiga pastki suvning zarari kam emas. Foydalaniladigan quduq tubiga suv oqimini cheklash neft konlarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish va neft qazib olishni ko'paytirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar tizimidagi eng muhim muammolardan biridir. Bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta mahsuldor qatlamlari ishlatadigan quduqlarda sug'orish notekis sodir bo'ladi - suv ko'proq o'tkazuvchan qatlamlar va oraliq qatlamlardan o'tadi. Ko'pgina hollarda, bunday qatlamlar orqali suv oqimi shunchalik kuchliki, quduq butunlay suv bosganga o'xshaydi. Bunday sharoitda alohida qatlamlarning notekis rivojlanishi sodir bo'ladi. Konlar va quduqlarning normal ishlashiga pastki suvning zarari kam emas.

Selektiv izolyatsiyalash usullari (SMI) - bu qatlamning butun teshilish qismiga AOK qilingan materiallardan foydalanadigan usullar. Bunda hosil bo'lgan cho'kma, gel yoki qattiqlashtiruvchi vosita faqat qatlamning suvga to'yingan qismida filtratsiya qarshiligini oshiradi va qatlamning neft qismining tiqilib qolishi sodir bo'lmaydi. SMI bilan qayta teshishning hojati yo'q.

Neft quduqlarining o'rtacha ko'rsatgichlari va suyuqlik tarkibi

1	Neft	3-10%	7	Ishqoriylik	2 mg.ekv/l
2	Suv	90-97%	8	Quruq qoldiq	118920 mg/l
3	G'ovaklilik	0,1-3 mm	9	Qattqlik	580 mg.ekv/l,
4	Zichlik	1,07 g/sm ³	10		200-360 atm
5	Yer osti bosimi	50-80 atm	11	O'tkazuvchanlik (suvda)	80-110 atm.
6	pH	6-8	12	Yer osti harorati	50-150 ⁰ C

XULOSA

GIPAN va boshqa ingidrientlar asosida olingan kompozision gidrogellarni olish va ularning fizik-kimyoviy xossalarini o'rganish yuqorida ko'rsatilgan usullar yordamida aniqlash, tajriba natijasida olingan natijalarning bir-biriga yaqinligidan dalolat beradi. Olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalaridagi tajriba xatoligi 2-3 % ni tashkil qiladi.

GIPAN o'zaro bog'lanishini o'rganish suvli eritmalarda initsiator ishtirokida amalga oshirildi. O'zaro bog'lash agenti miqdori GIPAN og'irligining 0,1-7% oralig'ida o'zgargan. Reaksiya haroratining o'zgarishi butun gellanish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi, shuning uchun 60⁰ C dan yuqori haroratlarda, reaksiya qisqa vaqt ichida davom etadi. Shunday qilib, 70⁰ C optimal harorat tanlangan, bunda gellanish bir necha daqiqada sodir bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Boltayeva, S. (2023). PREPARATION OF EMULSIONS FROM OIL EXTRACTS AND EVALUATION OF QUALITY INDICATORS. B CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (T.2 Выпуск 10, сс. 93-97).
2. Boltayeva Shahribonu Ahmad qizi. MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF CLOVE PLANT AND MEDICINE PREPARATION METHODS. (2023) Laboratorium Wiedzy Artur Borcuch (182-

185)

3. Boltayeva Shahribonu Ahmad qizi. Tirnoqgul o'simligining dorivorlik xususiyatlari va dori tayyorlash usullari. Analytical Journal of Education and Development. (14-17)

4. Bakhshullayevich, T. B., & Shaxina, S. (2022). Classification of Enzymes. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(5), 37-39.

5. Toxirov, B. B., Tagaeva, M. B., & Shukurova, S. (2023). Obtaining stabilized enzymes and their application in the food industry. Science and Education, 4(4), 529-537. Retrieved from <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/5560>

6. Tuyg'unovna, S. S. (2023). DORIVOR NA'MATAKNING FOYDALI XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIBBIYOTDA QO'LLANILISHI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(9), 11-13.

7. Shukurova, S. (2023). DORIVOR ACHCHIQ BODOM URUG'INING SHIFOBAXSHLIGI, DORI TAYYORLASH USULLARI. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(10 Part 3), 116-120.

8. Tuyg'unovna, S. S. (2023). USEFUL PROPERTIES OF THE MEDICINAL PRODUCT AND USE IN MEDICINE. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 40, 179-181.

9. Qobilovna, A. M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(09), 32-44.

10. Ataullayeva, M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A FUTURE SPECIALIST. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 109-114.

11. Qobilovna, A. M. (2021). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARIDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPITENTLIK SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK DETERMINANTLARI. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), (Special Issue), 102-105.

12. Narzulyeva, U., & Ismoilova, N. (2023). DETECTION OF EATING BEHAVIOR DISORDERS IN STUDENTS BEFORE THE EXAM USING THE DEBQ QUESTIONNAIRE. Наука и инновация, 1(15), 112-114.

13. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF MICROCIRCULATION DISORDERS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 60-65. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2811>

14. Нарзуллаева, У. Р., Самиева, Г. У., & Пардаева, З. С. (2020). Pathogenetic aspects of verified risk factors such as arterial hypertension and dyslipidemia in the development of chronic heart failure. American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 10(10), 776-779.

15. Narzulaeva Umida Rakhmatulloevna, Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna, & Ismatova Marguba Shaukatovna (2020). SPECIFICITY OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF THE INITIAL STAGES OF HYPERTENSION IN ARID ZONES OF UZBEKISTAN AND NON-DRUG APPROACHES TO TREATMENT. Кронос, (4 (43)), 15-17.

16. Umida Raxmatulloevna Narzulaeva, & Mohigul Abdurasulovna Bekkulova (2023). Arterial gipertenziya etiologiyasida dislipidemiyaning xavf omili sifatidagi roli. Science and Education, 4 (2), 415-419.

17. Narzulaeva, U. R., & Samieva, G. U. (2021). Nasirova ShSh. Hemoreological Disorders in The Early Stages Of Hypertension In Hot Climates. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice, 6(1), 221-225.

18. Axmedova, M. (2023). THE IMPACT OF SOCIOCULTURAL FACTORS ON THE PERVASIVENESS OF DENTAL CARIES AS A COMPLEX HEALTH CONDITION IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(9), 24-28.
19. Ostonova, G. (2023). ICHKI SEKRETSIYA BEZLARI FIZIOLOGIYASI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(10 Part 3), 110-115.
20. Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(9), 126-130.
21. Rakhimovna, T. D., & Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. *Conferencea*, 9-14.
22. Rahimova, G. (2023). МАКТАБЛАРДА BIOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. В *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION* (Т. 2, Выпуск 10, сс. 103–109).Zenodo.
23. Ахмедова, М. (2020). НАРУШЕНИЯ ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛЬНОЙ ФУНКЦИИ ПРИ РАЗВИТИИ АФТОЗНОГО СТОМАТИТА. *Достижения науки и образования*, (18 (72)), 65-69.
24. Axmedova, M. (2023). USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY AT THE STAGES OF DIAGNOSIS AND PLANNING ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT BASED ON ENDOSSEAL IMPLANTS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 54-58.
25. Ахмедова, М. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЭТАПАХ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ ОРТПЕДИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ЭНДОССАЛЬНЫХ ИМПЛАНТАТОВ. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 167-173.
26. Halimova, Y. S. (2023). Morphological Aspects of Rat Ovaries When Exposed to Caffeine Containing Drink. *BEST JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT*, 2(6), 294-300.
27. Халимова, Ю. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЯИЧНИКОВ КРЫС ПРИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ КОФЕИН СОДЕРЖАЩИХ НАПИТОК. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 23, 368-374.
28. Халимова, Ю. С., & Шокиров, Б. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ООБЕННОСТИ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ АЛКОГОЛИЗМЕ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 782-789.
29. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.
30. Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(6), 35-40.
31. Rasulov, Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 42(42).
32. Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC PHENOMENA OF A NATIONAL-CULTURAL NATURE, REPRESENTING MYTHOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(20), 19-24.
33. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim*

innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi, 9(5), 152-155.

34. Ergasheva, G. (2023). METHODS TO PREVENT SIDE EFFECTS OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN SICK PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(10), 104-108.

35. Ergasheva, G. T. (2022). QANDLI DIABET BILAN KASALLANGANLARDA REABILITATSIYA MEZONLARINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 335-337.

36. Rasulov, Z. (2023). The principle of cognitive economy as an important factor in information transmission. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 42(42).

37. Rasulov, Z. (2023). ПРИНЦИПЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ФОНАЦИОННОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 42(42).

38. Kazakova, N. N., & Sh, S. D. (2022). Evaluation of the prevalence and intensity of caries in children with rheumatism. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(5), 156-160.

39. Rasulov, Z., & Artikov, A. (2023, May). THE PRINCIPLE OF REDUNDANCY IN COMPOUND SENTENCES. In *Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes* (pp. 1-4).

40. Qobilovna, A. M. (2023). PROGRAM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FACTORS OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(11), 131-137.

41. Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POSITION OF TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(10), 31-42.

42. Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL CASE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(14), 9-15.

43. Джалилова, З. (2023). The notion of illocution in the theory of speech acts by John Austin. *Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке*, 1(1).

44. Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). ADAPTING TEACHING METHODS TO MODERN EDUCATIONAL TRENDS: PEDAGOGICAL ASPECT. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(10), 72-77.